

A Legal Appraisal of the Role of Court in Environmental Protection in Kenya: Lessons for Nigeria

Orluwosu, Franklin Nnamdi*

ABSTRACT

This article appraised the role of court in environmental protection in Kenya. The new constitutional regime in Kenya recognises right to the environment. The court is the arm of the government that work at ensuring that all the constitutionally guaranteed rights are enforced and safeguarded against any possible violation by state officials or any other person. This is also the case with the right to healthy and clean environment under the provision of auricle 42 of Constitution of Kenya 2010. The 2010 Kenyan Constitution has initiated a paradigm shift in the enforcement of environmental rights in the country. It is recommended that an environmental court should be created by the National Assembly of Nigeria through a specific law such as the situation in Kenya where the Environment and Land Court Act 2011 established a special court under section 4 saddled with the responsibility of adjudicating on matters relating to environmental right. This makes enforcement of such right by the court simpler and easier; there should be special procedure for the enforcement of environmental right as in Nigeria as it is in jurisdiction like Kenya; the government of Nigeria should make policy establishing and strengthening information disclosure systems/mechanisms between the public and institution in regards to state of the environment.

Keywords: Environmental Right, Human Right, Court

INTRODUCTION

Protection and enforcement of rights to environment remains a great challenge, especially in a developing country like Nigeria due to a number of factors which could include lack of institutional capacity, inadequate legislation, lack of competence of relevant enforcement officials to enforce existing legislation, and lack of information as well as national guidance materials on enforcement.¹ All of these and others may weaken the effectiveness of the law in relation to the protection and management of the environment hence, promoting environmental degradation. Therefore, enforcement remains a key factor for enabling national environmental laws to achieve their objectives of protecting and managing the environment from degradation.

The Environment and Land Court is a specialised court that has jurisdiction to adjudicate environmental disputes both originally and on appeal, and to review decisions of other relevant tribunals in certain instances. Such jurisdiction of the court includes its power to adjudicate disputes for redress of a violation, denial or infringement of, or threat to, rights or fundamental freedoms relating to a clean as well as healthy environment in the country as provided for under its 2010 Constitution.² The role of court in the protection of the environment and environmental right in Kenya is examined in this article.

* LL.B, BL, LL.M, Doctoral Candidate (RSU), Legal Practitioner, Email: franklinorluwosu29@gmail.com; 0803 671 2865.

¹ J G Frynas, 'Legal Change in Africa: Evidence from Oil-Related Litigation in Nigeria' [1999] (43) *J. Afr. L.*;121; I B Lawal and S A Fagbemi, 'An Appraisal of the Doctrines of Exhaustion, Ripeness and *Locus Standi* as mean to Preventing Frivolous Action Against Administrative Decisions in Nigeria' [2015] (6) (1) *EBSU Law Journal*;201.

² Environment and Land Court Act 2011, s 13(3).

Conceptual Framework

Environmental Right

Environmental right is a concept used in recognising human entitlement to specific environmental standards. Absence of a secure, unpolluted environment, human rights suffer, as well as sustainable environmental management is unattainable. Over one hundred constitutions across the globe now include the right to a healthy environment hence, acknowledging this correlation. These rights consist of substantive and procedural aspects.³ In this sense, substantive rights consist of civil, political, economic, social, cultural, as well as collective rights directly impacted by the environment. They include freedoms like association, non-discrimination, life, as well as rights to food, health, as well as that of a decent standard of living. These rights are enshrined in legal instruments, proffer tangible protections as well as benefits, distinguishable from procedural aspects of law.⁴ On the other hand, procedural rights are important in legal systems, detailing formal procedures for the enforcement and protection of rights, ensuring transparency and fairness. Key access rights comprise of information, justice, and public participation.⁵

Environmental rights can be defined as the right of the citizens of a nation to have a clean, safe as well as decent environment and to enforce the right in case of violation by private citizens or the government. This definition signifies the need to protect human health, interest and safety. This right requires the maintenance of a certain level of environment because of human use as well as enjoyment of nature.⁶ Thus, clean and healthy environment becomes a human right. It has further been submitted that, if enacted, environmental right would grant the public a right to healthy environment and also introduce a chain of reforms to increase the powers of the private citizens to protect themselves as well as their environment from the effects of pollution.⁷ Furthermore, such right would increase powers to sue in civil courts for damages caused by or resulted from pollution as well as to initiate private suits or claims for pollution where the government has refused to act. In addition, it would grant increased access to information on pollution as well as rights to participate on standard settings and other processes.⁸

Human Right

Human rights are seen as those rights inherent to every human being. Human rights define the relationships between individuals as well as power structures, particularly the State.⁹ Human rights are referred to as inherent entitlements inherent to every individual, independent of governmental recognition. These rights are universally applicable, regardless of citizenship, race, gender, religion, ethnicity or other distinctions, encompassing fundamental freedoms such as life, religion, and speech, as well as dignified necessities like food, employment, education, and healthcare.¹⁰

Human rights link people together by establishing a common framework of entitlements as well as obligations. The enjoyment of these rights centers on mutual respect from others, stressing the interconnectedness of human rights with responsibilities towards fellow individuals as well as the society at large. It is incumbent upon individuals to exercise their rights conscientiously, mindful of how their actions may impact the rights of others.¹¹

³ UNEP, 'What are Environmental Rights' <<https://www.unep.org/explore-topics/environmental-rights-and-governance/what-we-do/advancing-environmental-rights/what>> accessed 2 November 2025.

⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵ N H Worluh-Okolie, 'Human Rights Law and Environmental Protection: A Focus on Nigeria' [2024] 10 (3) *International Journal of Law*;17 <www.lawjournals.org> accessed 2 November 2025.

⁶ O Awolowo, 'Environmental Rights and Sustainable Development in Nigeria' [2017] 10 (06) *OIDA International Journal of Sustainable Development*;18 <<http://www.ssrn.com/link/OIDA-Intl-Journal-Sustainable-Dev.html>> accessed 2 November 2025.

⁷ *Ibid.*

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ B P Namene, 'Counter Terrorism and Observance of International Humanitarian Law Principles and Human Rights in Nigeria and United States of America' [2024] *Journal of Private and Property Law, Special Edition JUNE*;122 <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/395334652_COUNTER_TERRORISM_AND_OBSERVANCE_OF_INTERNATIONAL_HUMANITARIAN_LAW_PRINCIPLES_AND_HUMAN_RIGHTS_IN_NIGERIA_AND_UNITED_STATES_OF_AMERICA> accessed 2 November 2025.

¹⁰ United Nations, 'What are Human Rights?' <<https://www.ohchr.org/en/what-are-human-rights>> accessed 2 November 2025.

¹¹ *Ibid.*

An all-inclusive set of global human rights laws has been established to safeguard and for the advancement of basic rights as well as liberties within the framework of ecological sustainability. Major international agreements, such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1945 (UDHR), the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1966 (ICCPR), the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights 1966 (ICESCR), and regional human rights treaties, delineate rights relevant to environmental preservation and outline the responsibilities of states.¹² Additionally, environmental accords like the Paris Agreement¹³, the Convention on Biological Diversity 1992, and the Aarhus Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters 1998, complement human rights protocols by addressing environmental issues through collaborative approaches.¹⁴

Court

Courts may be defined as places concerned with settling legal disputes.¹⁵ It is a place where justice is administered or where a trial is held.¹⁶ A court is defined as a government body saddled with the adjudication of disputes and administration of justice. It consists of one or more judges who preside over matter brought before it.¹⁷ It is a place where justice is judicially administered or the judge or judges who sit in a court or an aggregate of separate courts judges.¹⁸ While a court can be described as a tribunal, not all tribunals are courts.¹⁹ The term “tribunal” refers to a body of people with power to determine issues of law and fact affecting the rights and obligations of people.²⁰ In this sense, a tribunal has a wider meaning than court. It extends to and includes court.²¹ It extends to and includes courts.

Appraisal of the Role of Courts in Environmental Protection in Kenya

The idea of environmental rights and justice is visibly centered upon principle 10 of the 1992 Rio Declaration on Environment and Development guaranteeing the rights of citizens to access information and justice in environment-related matters.²² This has been recognised by various national and regional laws and entrenched in constitutions and legal instruments as it ensures accountability, transparency and inclusiveness in environmental governance.²³ Accordingly, the constitutions of many countries including Kenya recognise environmental rights and protection and frameworks for their enforcement.

The right to life has been interpreted in most cases to include environmental rights where there is absence of such provision.²⁴ The increasing global acceptance of a recurring overlap of human rights, justice and the environment is informing the widespread consideration of environmental rights as part of human rights, largely influenced by international environmental law and multilateral environmental agreements. Enforcement of this right makes it very useful and well protected or guaranteed. Nevertheless, in the Nigerian context, there are certain legal impediments to the enforcement of environmental rights. Prominent among

¹² N H Worluh-Okolie, ‘Human Rights Law and Environmental Protection: A Focus on Nigeria’ [2024] 10 (3) *International Journal of Law*;16 <www.lawjournals.org> accessed 2 November 2025.

¹³ ‘The Paris Agreement’ <<https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement>> accessed 2 November 2025.

¹⁴ Worluh-Okolie (n14) 16.

¹⁵ A Taiwo, *The Principles, Practice and Procedure of Civil Litigation in Nigeria* (Ababa Press Limited 2015) 51.

¹⁶ O O Ogwezzzy, ‘History and Organization of Courts System in Nigeria’ [2018] 1 *AGORA International Journal of Juridical Sciences*;21 <<http://univagora.ro/jour/index.php/aijjs>> accessed 2 November 2025.

¹⁷ B A Garner (ed), *Black’s Law Dictionary* (6th edn: St Paul, Minn West Publishing Company 1990) 378.

¹⁸ E Jowitt, *Jowitt’s Dictionary of English Law* (London: 2nd edn, Sweet & Maxwell 1977) 493.

¹⁹ O N Ogbu, *Modern Nigerian Legal System* (Enugu: 2nd edn, Cidjap Press 2007) 202.

²⁰ *Ibid.*

²¹ *Ibid.*

²² R T Ako, ‘The Judicial Recognition and Enforcement of the Right to Environment: Differing Perspectives from Nigeria and India’ [2010] (3) *National University of Juridical Sciences Law Review*;423.

²³ D L Shelton and E M Duer, ‘Human Rights and the Environment’ in L Kurukulasuriya and N Robinson (eds), *UNEP Training Manual on International Environmental Law* (Nairobi: UNEP 2006) 301 <<https://www.unenvironment.org/resources/report/unep-training-manual-international-environmental-law>> accessed 3 November 2025.

²⁴ K Khoday, ‘Environmental Justice – Comparative Experiences in Legal Empowerment’ (Working Paper, United Nations Development Programme – UNDP, 12 June 2014) 5 <www.undp.org/content/undp/en/home/librarypage/democratic-governance/access_to_justiceandruleoflaw/environmental-justice-comparative-experiences> accessed 3 November 2025.

them are the recognition of such right in the non-justiciable chapter of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) (CFRN).²⁵

Non-domestication of relevant international environmental law and multilateral environmental agreements on the right to the environment further hamper the enforcement of environmental rights in Nigeria. Nigeria is one of the State Parties to the 1969 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (VCLT) which provides that all the signatories thereto shall always ensure the implementation of international treaties in their jurisdictions in good faith.²⁶ Furthermore, the CFRN and African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights 1981 domesticated by Nigeria in 1983 as African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Enforcement and Ratification) Act (ACHPRERA) both mandate the Federal Government of Nigeria to ensure that environmental rights of Nigerians are protected.²⁷ In addition, the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act (NESREA Act) empowers National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) to enforce compliance with the provisions of international agreements, protocols, conventions and treaties on the environment.²⁸

However, the environmental obligations of Nigerian Government are seriously hindered by the provision of section 12 of the CFRN 1999 (as amended) providing that a treaty to which Nigeria is a party can only have the force of law in the country if enacted into law by the National Assembly.²⁹ The contradictory provisions of the CFRN, VCLT, NESREA Act, and the ACHPRERA have hindered the implementation of relevant international environmental law and multilateral environmental agreements in Nigeria. It has been argued that certain international environmental law and multilateral environmental agreements, the VCLT and federal legislation in Nigeria like the NESREA Act are inconsistent with the constitutional requirement for the domestication of a treaty before it can have the force of law.³⁰ However, it could be submitted that having ratified the VCLT, any international environmental law and multilateral environmental agreements that the Nigerian Government ratifies should become binding or at least strongly persuasive and the Government of Nigeria is under the duty (in good faith) to ensure the domestication and implementation of such international environmental law and multilateral environmental agreements because the treaty was so ratified pursuant to the government's constitutional environmental obligations to Nigerians.³¹

Generally, it is expected that the processes involved in domesticating a treaty actually begins with its ratification at the international level. Thus, it is argued that the Nigerian legislature and the courts should always frown at the ratification of treaties by the executive arm of government just for the sake of international political correctness, only to turn around and refuse to domesticate the treaty, thereby misleading the citizens for whom the government holds state power in trust for their welfare and security, which includes a cleaner as well as sustainable environment.³²

It is further argued that for the reason that the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights 1981 (ACHPR), which recognises the right of all peoples to a generally satisfactory environment, has been domesticated in Nigeria since 1983 as ACHPRERA, the right to a clean environment could be regarded as an integral part of the human rights of Nigerians as recognised under Chapter II of the CFRN and must be enforced like any other human rights. The Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules 2009, made for the enforcement of Chapter IV of the CFRN, equally directs the enforcement of the ACHPR and other International Bills of Rights in Nigeria.³³ This may make ratified (but non-domesticated) international environmental right instruments enforceable or at least strongly persuasive because by virtue of the directive of the Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules 2009 (FREPR), environmental rights as a human

²⁵ CFRN 1999 (as amended), s 20.

²⁶ Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, 1969, arts 26 and 27.

²⁷ ACHPRERA 1983, art 24.

²⁸ NESREA Act, 2007, s 7(c).

²⁹ (n25), s 12.

³⁰ M U Ukponu, 'Environmental Law and Access to Justice in Nigeria: A Case for a Specialised National Environment and Planning Tribunal (NEPT)' [2019] (1) (1) *NAU Law Review*;31.

³¹ (n25), s 20.

³² Ukponu (30) 32.

³³ Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules 2009; CFRN 1999 (as amended), preamble 3 (a) and (b) (i) and (ii), (c) and (d) and II (1).

right have been “domesticated by reference”.³⁴ Hence, by virtue of the provision of the FREPR employed to enforce the ACHPR, there has been expansion of the boundaries of human rights to include environmental rights.³⁵

The current position of the law in Nigeria is that a ratified treaty remains unenforceable or at best merely persuasive so long as it has not been domesticated. Thus, there is need for a legislative review of this position to the extent that upon ratification of a particular treaty, the executive arm of government is expected to submit it to the legislature for domestication, and there is need for a time frame for such action. Accordingly, judicial environmental activism is encouraged in this regard. It is argued in this article that the courts should always regard ratified treaties as strongly persuasive, especially in matters that have direct impact on the security and welfare of Nigerians, such as environmental rights and protection. This will indicate commitment on the part of the Nigerian judiciary in the enforcement of environmental rights such as is the case in Kenya.

It is cheering to state that the Kenyan Constitution of 2010 seeks to encourage enhancement of access to justice in relation to environmental rights litigation in two major ways. The first is that unlike in other types of litigation, an environmental rights litigant does not need to prove that he or she has suffered injury to get relief from the courts.³⁶ The constitution of Kenya makes the proof of environmental rights easier as it clearly removes environmental case from the list of cases that relief can only be granted upon proof of the case on a balance of probabilities. Thus, in the litigation concerning the enforcement of environmental rights, this requirement is waived. Thus, in Kenya, most environmental cases are proved using scientific imperatives that require highly trained experts to demonstrate the injury suffered.³⁷

An important point to be noted in the case of enforcement of environmental rights is the fact the 2010 Constitution has relaxed the requirement for *locus standi* in a litigation concerning enforcement of environmental rights.³⁸ The Constitution is very clear on this that the person taking an action to court need not be the victim of the environmental harm or threatened harm.³⁹ This type of situation gives wide room to environmental activists and whistle-blowers in the Non-Governmental Organisation (NGO) sector to encourage the enforcement of rights to the environment in Kenya. Most ordinary citizens do not understand their basic rights due to ignorance and poverty. The position as introduced by the Kenyan Constitution makes it possible for vigilant activists to take up legal action on behalf of vulnerable groups. The new provisions of the Constitution grant environmental whistle-blowers as well as other public-spirited interest groups the opportunity to actually challenge any decision or action that may impact on the environment in a negative manner. This change of approach is bound to extensively change the landscape of environmental rights litigation in the Kenya.⁴⁰

The new constitutional arrangement in Kenya has also dealt with the challenge of undue technicalities that used to frustrate environmental rights litigants in the country before the enactment of the 2010 Constitution. The Constitution provides under article 159(2)(d) that “In exercising judicial authority, the courts and tribunals shall be guided by the following principles... justice shall be administered without undue regard to procedural technicalities...”⁴¹ In the past, several critical environmental matters were dismissed on ground of technicalities without consideration of their merits. One of such matters was the case of *Wangari Mathai v Kenya Times Media Trust*.⁴² In denying the plaintiff *locus standi*, Justice Dugdale ruled that “it is well established that only the Attorney-General (AG) can sue on behalf of the public”.⁴³

The court was faced with similar facts on requirements for *locus standi* in the case of *Maina Kamanda and Another v Nairobi City Council*,⁴⁴ per Justice Akilano Akiwumi. The argument of the defendants in the

³⁴ Ukponu (n30) 32.

³⁵ (n33).

³⁶ Constitution of Kenyan 2010, art 70(3).

³⁷ J K Bosek, ‘Implementing Environmental Rights in Kenya’s New Constitutional Order: Prospects and Potential Challenges’ [2014] (14) *African Human Rights Law Journal (AHRLJ)*;501.

³⁸ (n36).

³⁹ *Ibid*, art 22(2).

⁴⁰ Bosek (n37).

⁴¹ (n36), art 159(2)(d).

⁴² (1989) 1 KLR (E&L).

⁴³ *Ibid*.

⁴⁴ Unreported: Nairobi High Court Civil Case (1992) 6153.

present case was that the plaintiff had no standing to institute the action, since he required the permission of the AG to bring such action, which he had not obtained. In dismissing this contention of the defendants, the presiding judge quoted with approval the decision in the English case of *IRC v National Federation of Self-Employed and Small Business Limited*.⁴⁵ The learned justice held thus: “I think that it is now well settled that a ratepayer, as opposed to a tax payer, has sufficient interest as such, to challenge in court the action of a public body to whose expenses he contributes.”⁴⁶

The entrenchment and prioritisation of environmental rights under the 2010 Constitution of Kenya is underscored by the fact that a specialised court has been designated to deal with environmental disputes. The Constitution empowers the parliament to establish courts with the status of a high court to hear and determine disputes relating to the environment and the use as well as occupation of, and title to land.⁴⁷ Accordingly, Kenyan parliament enacted the Environment and Land Court Act which establishes the Environment and Land Court (ELC) as a specialised court handling environmental and land cases.⁴⁸ The court is given the status of a high court.

The overriding objective of the enabling Act⁴⁹ is to enable the court to facilitate the expeditious, just, proportionate as well as accessible resolution of disputes governed by the Act.⁵⁰ The ELC has both original and appellate jurisdiction to hear as well as determine all disputes in accordance with article 162(2) (b) of the 2010 Kenyan Constitution and with the provisions of the Act or any other law applicable in the country relating to environment and land.⁵¹ Further, in exercise of its jurisdiction under article 162(2) (b) of the Kenyan Constitution 2010, the court has power to hear and determine disputes, relating to environmental protection and planning, climate issues, land use planning, tenure, title, boundaries, rents, rates, valuations, minerals, mining and other natural resources; relating to compulsory acquisition of land; land administration and management; public, private and community land and contracts, choses in action or any other instruments granting any enforceable interests in land; as well as any other dispute relating to land and environment.⁵²

The ELC is also empowered to hear and determine applications for redress of a denial, violation or infringement of, or threat to, rights or fundamental freedom concerning a clean as well as healthy environment under articles 42, 69 as well as 70 of the Kenyan Constitution of 2010.⁵³ The ELC may make any order as well as grant any relief as it deems fit and just, together with, interim or permanent preservation orders as well as injunctions; prerogative orders; award of damages; compensation; specific performance; declaration; restitution; or costs.⁵⁴ Therefore, it is clear that environmental rights in Kenya are well entrenched under the country’s Constitution and specific statute, and the court plays a special role in ensuring the actualisation and enforcement of this right.

However, it is worth noting that even before the current 2010 Constitution of Kenya, Courts in the country still successfully handled environmental matters as a way of encouraging enforcement. For example, in the case of *Waweru v Republic*,⁵⁵ the Court reiterated the position of section 3 of Environment (Management and Conservation) Act 1999 (EMCA) which requires that courts take certain universal principles into consideration when determining environmental cases. It also went further to state that apart from the EMCA it was of the view that the principles set out in section 3 do constitute part of international customary law and the courts ought to take cognisance of them in all the relevant situations. Therefore, it reiterated that courts had and still has a role in promoting sustainable development. The Court in this case was to deal with four principles which it considered directly relevant to the matter at hand which were: sustainable development; precautionary principle; polluter pays; and public trust (not spelt out in EMCA).⁵⁶

⁴⁵ (1982) AC 617 740.

⁴⁶ *Ibid*.

⁴⁷ (n36), art 162(2)(b).

⁴⁸ Environment and Land Court Act 2011, s 4.

⁴⁹ Environment and Land Court Act 2011.

⁵⁰ *Ibid*, s 3(1).

⁵¹ *Ibid*, s 13(1).

⁵² *Ibid*, s 13(2).

⁵³ *Ibid*, s 13(3).

⁵⁴ *Ibid*, s 13(7).

⁵⁵ (2007) AHRLR 149 (KeHC 2006).

⁵⁶ *Ibid*, para 25.

Courts are significant players in promoting as well as securing the environmental rights of persons and in environmental conservation and are thus useful in achievement of peace, sustainable development as well as environmental justice for all. Therefore, this means that the role of courts in environmental matters cannot be dispensed with.⁵⁷

The ELC of Kenya, has been reasonably instrumental in the development of strong jurisprudence on environmental sustainability as well as protection of the right to a clean and healthy environment in the country. In the case of *Moffat Kamau and 9 Others v Aelous Kenya Limited and 9 Others (Wind Farm Project)*,⁵⁸ the first respondent in the instant case was granted a licence for development of a 30-megawatt wind farm. This was later expanded to 60 megawatts without undergoing a new environmental impact assessment (EIA).⁵⁹ The argument of the claimants was that the wind farm violated their right to a clean as well as healthy environment by transforming their agrarian landscape into an industrial site for electricity generation.⁶⁰ The argument of the respondents was that the project was supported by the government and was aligned with country's economic blueprint document (Vision 2030).⁶¹ It was further argued that it was a green project that would produce green energy as well as benefit the Kenyan economy.⁶² The ELC declared that the failure to abide by the EIA regulations violated the petitioners' right to a clean and healthy environment and also pointed out that it would not hesitate to identify mistakes where they have occurred as well as to demand adherence to proper procedures, in spite of the project's significance because the greater duty of the court is to safeguard the environment for present as well as future generations.⁶³ Further even though the EIA regulations were silent on the need for a new EIA Study Report before an EIA variation licence could be issued, the ELC invoked Regulation 28 of the EIA Regulations and thus held that where there is substantial change that goes to the substance of the project, it should be deemed as a new project which requires a new EIA licence, meaning that a fresh EIA have to be carried out.⁶⁴

In *African Centre for Rights and Governance and 3 Others v Municipal Council of Naivasha (ACRAG)*,⁶⁵ the respondent had been using a piece of land as a dumpsite for disposal of solid waste generated within the Naivasha Municipal Council.⁶⁶ The applicant approached the ELC seeking a declaratory order that "the violation of article 42 of the Constitution, 2010, by the respondent has resulted in a denial of the right to a clean and healthy environment to the petitioners and residents of Naivasha Municipality"⁶⁷ as well as a mandatory injunction for the relocation of the dumpsite and a prohibitory injunction to cease any dumping of waste.⁶⁸ The ELC conducted an on-site inspection as well as indicated that where evidence—even if not conclusive—shows risks to health as the consequence of the operation of the illegal dumping site, this may be sufficient to find the right to a clean and healthy environment violated as well as declared that the right to a clean and healthy environment had been violated.⁶⁹ Although, the court did not order the closure of the dumpsite, as it considered the lack of an alternative site for waste disposal, it ordered the respondent to ensure daily collection as well as incineration of plastic bags, and to apply for the requisite licence from NEMA to use the site as a dumpsite, to undertake a thorough EIA as well as consider an option of having a landfill instead of an open dumpsite.⁷⁰

⁵⁷ K Muigua, 'The Role of Courts in Safeguarding Environmental Rights in Kenya: A Critical Appraisal' [2019];18 <<http://kmco.co.ke/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/The-Role-of-Courts-in-Safeguarding-Environmental-Rights-in-Kenya-A-Critical-Appraisal-Kariuki-Muigua-17th-January-2019-1.pdf>> accessed 3 November 2025.

⁵⁸ (2016) KEELC 565 (KLR).

⁵⁹ *Ibid*, para 3.

⁶⁰ *Ibid*, para 7.

⁶¹ *Ibid*, para 41.

⁶² *Ibid*, para 22.

⁶³ *Ibid*, para 95.

⁶⁴ *Ibid*, para 83.

⁶⁵ Petition No 50 of 2012 (2017) eKLR.

⁶⁶ *Ibid*, para 1.

⁶⁷ *Ibid*, para 2.

⁶⁸ *Ibid*, para 2.

⁶⁹ *Ibid*, para 33.

⁷⁰ *Ibid*, para 43.

The ELC gave judgment in favour of the petitioners in the landmark decision of *Kelvin Musyoke and 9 others v The Hon Attorney General and 7 others (Musyoke)*,⁷¹ and made a declaration that the Owino Uhuru community was entitled to their right to a clean as well as healthy environment, right to the highest attainable standard of health as well as right to clean and safe water as guaranteed by article 43 of the Constitution with right to life as guaranteed by the provisions of article 26 of the Constitution of Kenya.⁷² The court also granted the petitioners compensation to the amount of Kshs 1.3 billion for personal injury and loss of life, payable by Kenyan Government and the two companies whose industrial activities had actually resulted in lead poisoning, which had negatively affected both persons and the environment.⁷³ Additionally, the court directed the respondents to clean up the soil and water as well as remove any waste deposited within the settlement within four months of the date of judgment.⁷⁴

The recent decision in Kenya in the case of *Metal Refinery (EPZ) Ltd v Owino Uhuru Residents*,⁷⁵ has set prevailing precedents for the promotion as well as protection of the right to a healthy environment in the country and the role of court in ensuring that right to the environment is well entrenched and enforced. This case highlights the critical role of the court in upholding constitutional and environmental rights. The case centers on the environmental impact of a lead-acid battery recycling factory operated by Metal Refinery (EPZ) Ltd. in Owino-Uhuru community, Mombasa County. The residents of the community alleged that toxic waste from the factory operated by the company led to severe health problems, as well as led to poisoning and many deaths. The National Environment Management Authority (NEMA) of Kenya had initially issued an environmental impact assessment license to the factory. Although, in spite of concerns about pollution, the NEMA failed in the enforcement of necessary environmental safeguards. Instead of halting the operations, NEMA allowed company to conduct “test runs” to assess the environmental impact of its discharges. The ELC found that NEMA, along with other state agencies, failed to uphold environmental protections, leading to the continued operations of the factory regardless of clear environmental harm. Damages amounting to Kshs. 1.3 billion was awarded by the ELC for loss of life and personal injury and total of Kshs. 700 million for environmental restoration. The case was later reviewed by the Court of Appeal (CA), modifying the allocation of liability as well as revising the award of damages. The matter was further appealed to the Supreme Court (SC). The latter examined whether NEMA had the legal authority to permit “test runs” and whether the CA correctly assessed liability and damages.

The court held inter alia that the constitutional provision on the enforcement of the right to clean as well as healthy environment was basically based on the polluter pays principle where the provisions gave wide power to the court to compel the government or any other public agency to take restorative measures as well as to provide compensation for any victim of pollution and to compensate the costs borne by the victims for the lost use of natural resources as a result of an act of pollution. In addition to the polluter pays principle, there was also the precautionary principle which directly impacted on environmental liability. Section 3(5) of the Environmental Management and Conservation Act (EMCA) 1999 embodied the principles to guide the courts at arriving at a determination in an application for redress for a contravention to a clean and healthy environment.⁷⁶

Lessons for Nigeria

It is clear that the new constitutional regime in Kenya recognises right to the environment.⁷⁷ The court is the arm of the government that work at ensuring that all the constitutionally guaranteed rights are enforced and safeguarded against any possible violation by state officials or any other person. This is also the case with the right to healthy and clean environment in Kenya.⁷⁸ The 2010 Kenyan Constitution has initiated a paradigm shift in the enforcement of environmental rights in the country. Enforcement of environmental rights in Kenya is well entrenched and streamlined. This is a great lesson for Nigeria in order to ensure the enjoyment of the right to environment in the country. Public interest litigation in court for the enforcement of environmental

⁷¹ (2020) eKLR.

⁷² *Ibid*, para 168.

⁷³ *Ibid*, para 171.

⁷⁴ *Ibid*, para 171.

⁷⁵ [2024] KESC 75 (KLR).

⁷⁶ *Ibid*.

⁷⁷ (n36).

⁷⁸ *Ibid*, art 42.

right in Kenya is promoted. The Constitution is very clear on this under its article 22(2) promoting the fact that person taking an action to court need not be the victim of the environmental harm or threatened harm.⁷⁹ This gives wide room to environmental activists and whistle-blowers in the Nongovernmental Organisations (NGOs) sector to encourage the enforcement of rights to the environment in the country. This is a good lesson to learn as most victims of environmental rights violation are ignorant and poor. In Kenya, the court is encouraged to disregard technicalities and do substantial justice to environmental matters. Considering the fact that the court is usually congested leading to delay in the determination of cases, a special court is established in Kenya for the enforcement of environmental rights in the country. Kenya legislature enacted the Environment and Land Court Act (ELC Act) in 2011 as a way of ensuring efficient enforcement of environmental right in the country. The ELC Act established Environment and Land Court (ELC) with the status of a high court of justice in the country.⁸⁰ The ELC created specifically to handle environmental and land matters is a decision to stand Kenya out in Africa as country with better enforcement measure for environmental protection.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Constitutions of many nations contain specific provisions aimed at the protection of the environment and benefits or interests concerning the environment. Most of the world's people live under the constitutions that have provisions for the protection of the environment. Such provision of the constitution protecting the environment comes in several forms. Such provisions can be enforceable like in the case of Kenya or unenforceable, if not, they are considered matters of directive principles of state policy that are generally designed to galvanise, though not compel, legislative activity for the protection of the environment. This is the practice under the provision of section 20 of the CFRN 1999 (as amended).

The following recommendations have been made in view of the matters discussed above;

- i. An environmental court should be created by the National Assembly of Nigeria through a specific law such as the situation in Kenya where the Environment and Land Court Act 2011 established a special court under section 4 saddled with the responsibility of adjudicating on matters relating to environmental right. This makes enforcement of such right by the court simpler and easier.
- ii. There should be special procedure for the enforcement of environmental right as in Nigeria as it is in jurisdiction like Kenya.
- iii. The government of Nigeria should make policy establishing and strengthening information disclosure systems/mechanisms between the public and institutions in regards to state of the environment.

⁷⁹ *Ibid*, art 22(2).

⁸⁰ (n2), s 4(2) and (2).